

**IMPLEMENTATION OF THE NATIONAL LEARNING CAMP THROUGH THE
DIFFERENT LEARNING FOCUS: ITS IMPACT TO PUPILS'
ENGAGEMENT AND LEARNING PERFORMANCE**

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Implementation of the National Learning Camp through the Different Learning Focus: Its Impact to Pupils' Engagement and Learning Performance

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Abstract

The study attempted to determine the influence of the implementation of the National Learning Camp through different learning focuses on pupils' engagement and learning performance. Descriptive-correlational research method was utilized and the Statistical tools used in the study were mean, standard deviation, frequency count, and percentages to analyze the extent of the implementation of learning camp in terms of enhancement, consolidation, and intervention; learning performance, and the significant relationship between the pupils' learning engagement and performance and the learning focus. Pearson-Product Moment Correlation was utilized to ascertain the significant relationship between the level of pupils' learning performance and the extent of learning focus as well as the pupils' learning performance and learning engagement. Findings revealed that enhancement, consolidation, and intervention were always and most of time practiced, respectively. Pupils had the "satisfactory" learning performance and very highly engaged to the different learning focus. It was also found out that enhancement and consolidation were correlated to pupils' learning performance while intervention was not correlated to pupils' learning performance. Additionally, pupils' learning engagement was not correlated with pupils' learning performance. Subsequently, it was recommended to the Schools Division Superintendent, School Principal, and Teachers to continue to design an effective framework for teaching-learning initiative which are learner-centered to intensify learners' engagement and improve learning performance.

Keywords: *learning camp, enhancement, consolidation, intervention, learning engagement and performance*

Introduction

Learning does not only take place in the traditional and regular classroom because pupils are more interested and engaged in learning from different modalities, contexts, and settings within the distinct learning landscape such as the learning camp. The learning camp provides an important setting for learning and developing social and emotional learning skills.

The study is anchored on DO 14, s. 2023 dated July 3, 2023 also known as the policy guidelines on the implementation of National Learning Camp in line with the MATATAG: *Bansang Makabata, Batang Makabansa* agenda. This policy contributes to the commitment of the Department of Education to the National Learning Recovery Program which aims to close learning gaps and assist the K to 12 learners in all public elementary and secondary schools nationwide in attaining learning standards.

The implementation of the national learning camp program helps accelerate learning and quality education in the public schools as the intervention, consolidation, and enhancement programs are provided through the distinct learning experiences which stimulates pupils' learning and academic performance.

Manuel (2020) pointed out that pupils learn, develop, and grow meaningfully across contexts and settings can support lessons learned elsewhere or may offer contradictions or challenges to previous lessons. Learning camp is an essential intervention for learners to develop and enhance their cognitive skills through varied, learner-centered, and fun learning activities to improve learning outcomes.

The learning camp is based on the specific needs of the learners, they shall be enrolled any of the three (3) camps; namely, Enhancement Camp, Consolidation Camp, and Intervention Camp. The Enhancement Camp enriches learning for advanced learners by providing greater depth, breadth, and complexity of learning areas competencies while the Consolidation Camp provides further practice on and application of previously taught competencies. Opportunities are provided to identify links connecting concepts and skills across grade-level competencies.

Additionally, the Intervention Camp supports learners who are not yet grasp foundational Mathematics, Science, and/or foundational English language skills. Recognizing the critical role of teachers in improving learning outcomes. The implementation of the national learning camp of the Department of Education has two-fold purposes, namely; improving learners' learning performance and strengthening teachers' teaching competence.

Henderson, et al (2020) posited that learning camp is a type of learning setting including extracurricular activities, organized sports, arts and music, youth groups, and summer-based activities are more important contributors to the growth of social and emotional learning, identify development, and the supports for positive development of every learner.

However, the implementation of national learning camp focuses only on the remediation of the different learning areas with particular emphasis on Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics-Reading (STEM-R). STEM disciplines and reading shall go hand in hand as the former require the interpretation of the technical texts, content specific vocabulary, and critical thinking, and the ability to clearly communicate these complex concepts to others verbally and in writing while allowing learners to gain skills in problem solving,

exploratory learning, and critical thinking.

Conversely, the National Learning Camp (NLC) in its implementation may encounter several issues such as parents' cooperation of the program and pupils' participation since attendance is voluntary in nature.

It is based on this circumstance that the researcher is stimulated to conduct this study to ascertain the impact of the national learning camp to pupil-participants in terms of intervention, consolidation, and enhancement programs.

Research Questions

The study aimed to ascertain the impact of the national learning camp through different learning focus to pupils' engagement and performance. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of implementation of the National Learning Camp in Baluarte Elementary School in terms of the following learning focus;
 - 1.1. enhancement;
 - 1.2. consolidation; and,
 - 1.3. intervention?
2. What is the level of pupils' engagement of the different learning focus when they are categorized as;
 - 2.1. extremely high engagement;
 - 2.2. high engagement;
 - 2.3. moderate engagement;
 - 2.4. low engagement; and,
 - 2.5. no engagement?
3. What is the level of pupils' learning performance when they are categorized as;
 - 3.1. outstanding;
 - 3.2. very satisfactory;
 - 3.3. satisfactory;
 - 3.4. fairly satisfactory; and,
 - 3.5. did not meet expectation?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the pupils' engagement in different learning focus and the implementation of the national learning camp .
5. Is there a significant relationship between pupils' learning performance and the pupils' engagement in different focus?

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized descriptive-correlational research design. Descriptive research according to Calderon, et al (2019) is a fact-finding inquiry or investigation. It is employed to develop a thorough knowledge of the primary causes of the given situations.

In addition, descriptive-correlational design as an inquiry used an in-depth analysis of the problem which data collection methods include, but not limited to the survey questionnaire and the like.

Subsequently, descriptive-correlational research design is used to quantify the problem by way of generating numerical data or data that can be transformed into usable statistics. This method measures variables through the use of quantifiable or finite data and the analysis was based on generated information from statistical tools. This method is also used in an inquiry with larger population.

Successively, descriptive data gathering procedures comprise different types of gathering information such as, but not limited to, the use of survey questionnaires, interview, and focused-group discussion (FGD).

Respondents

The respondents of the study are the pupils of Baluarte Elementary School in Sitio Baluarte, Lumbia, Cagayan de Oro City.

There were sixty-five (65) pupil-respondents of the study who answered the survey questionnaire on the implementation of the national learning camp, respectively. The respondents were purposively chosen because of their number and for the convenient accessibility of the researcher.

Instrument

This study adapted the research instrument of Manuel (2020) who asserted that pupils learn, develop, and grow meaningfully across contexts and settings can support lessons learned elsewhere or may offer contradictions or challenges to previous lessons

The survey instrument is composed of three (3) major components. The first component is on the implementation of the national learning camp based on different learning focus with ten (10) indicators. The second component is on pupils' engagement and learning

performance with ten (10) indicators.

Further, the third component is on pupils' learning performance which measure pupils' academic performance for the given academic year which are categorized as outstanding, very satisfactory, satisfactory, fairly satisfactory, and did not meet expectations.

Procedure

The researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent through the recommendation of the Dean of the Graduate School and thesis adviser to conduct the study in the City Division of Cagayan de Oro.

The same permission shall be asked by the researcher to the teacher-respondents to participate in the study and to the parents of pupils-respondents to allow the researcher utilize their child's learning performance as the variable of this study. Moreover, the parents were assured that the data gathered be treated to its highest confidentiality and used for research purposes only.

After the respondents provided the data, the researcher retrieved the said questionnaire, summarized, tabulated, and submitted for analysis to the Statistician using appropriate statistical tools and techniques.

Data Analysis

The following statistical treatment are utilized to answer the different problems presented:

For Problem 1, mean and standard deviation were used to determine the extent of the implementation of national learning camp based on the different learning focus.

For Problem 2, mean and standard deviation were used to determine the pupils' engagement to different focus.

For Problem 3, frequency and percentages were used to present the pupils' learning performance..

For Problem 4, Pearson r was utilized to ascertain significant relationship between the extent of the implementation of the national learning camp and the level of pupils' engagement to different focus.

For Problem 5, Pearson r was utilized to determine the significant relationship between the pupils' learning performance and their engagement to different focus.

Results and Discussion

This chapter comprises the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the finding resulting from this study on the Implementation of the National Learning Camp Through the Different Learning Focus its Impact to Pupils' Engagement and Learning Performance. The analysis and interpretation of data is carried out based on the problem presented.

Problem 1. What is the Extent of the Implementation of National Learning Camp in Baluarte Elementary School in terms of the following learning focus; Enhancement; Consolidation; Intervention?

The implementation of the National Learning Camp of the Department of Education aims to create a camp-like learning atmosphere where teachers integrate fun and more engaging activities that foster pupils' learning interest, socio-emotional skills, personal growth, and character development. The program was designed to close the learning gaps and assist the K to 12 learners in the public schools nationwide in attaining learning standards.

Table 1.1 shows the mean distribution of National Learning Camp in terms of Enhancement.

Table 1.1. *Mean Distribution of National Learning Camp in terms of Enhancement*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Inspires learner to work independently	4.27	.484	Always
2. Enriches learning for advanced students	4.27	.484	Always
3. Provides complex yet interesting learning experiences	4.27	.515	Always
4. Provides extensive learning experiences	4.24	.500	Always
5. Provides activities that develop critical thinking skills	4.23	.523	Always
6. Develops higher order thinking skills of learners	4.23	.552	Always
7. Facilitates deep understanding of the real world context.	4.14	.555	Most of the Time
8. Enriches current knowledge, skills, and understanding of learning area competencies	4.07	.509	Most of the Time
9. Facilitates advanced learning in English, Science, and Mathematics	4.07	.509	Most of the Time
10. Cultivates positive learning environment	4.07	.509	Most of the Time
Overall Mean	4.19	.514	Most of the Time

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Always/3.41-4.20 Most of the Time/2.61-3.40 Sometimes/1.81-2.60 Seldom/1.00-1.80 Never

Table 1.1 displays the mean distribution of the implementation of the National Learning Camp program of the Department of Education in terms of enhancement. Overall, the respondents rated the enhancement "Most of the Time" with a mean of 4.19 (SD=.514). This result indicates that the national learning camp helps pupils develop deeper understanding of the relevance of learning, enrich current knowledge, enriching knowledge in English, Science, and Mathematics as well as in cultivating positive learning environment.

As pointed out by Manuel (2020), learning outside the normal classroom provides opportunities to pupils to experience learning in a meaningfully and more engaging venue outside the classroom where everyone learns across contexts and informal settings.

Additionally, it was emphasized that learning camp offers an interesting environment where learners gain support from each other in an informal learning situation. Learning camp is an essential intervention for learners to develop and enhance their cognitive skills through varied, learner-centered, and fun learning activities to improve learning outcomes.

The indicators “Inspires learners to work independently”, “enriches learning for advanced students”, and “provides complex yet interesting learning experiences” obtained the highest mean value of 4.27 (SD=.484) which is verbally described as “always” which indicate that the learning camp encourages learners to work in their academic tasks more interestingly and provide them the most interesting learning experiences.

Manuel (2020) explains that the learning camp provides an enhancement training to learners where the activities are designed to provide opportunities to learners which learning challenges to learn with fun in a less formal environment.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 4.07 (SD=.509) which is verbally described as “Most of the Time” in the indicators “enriches current knowledge, skills, and understanding of learning area competencies”, “facilitates advanced learning in English, Science, and Mathematics”, and “cultivates positive learning environment”. The results indicate that the learning camp occasionally provide an enriched learning environment for pupils to learn in different settings where they were given an opportunity to improve their least mastered competencies.

Creswell and Plano (2021) averred that the learning camp create a camp-like atmosphere by integrating fun and engaging activities to foster learner interests, socio-emotional skills, personal growth, and character development.

Table 1.2. Mean Distribution of National Learning Camp in terms of Consolidation

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
1. Learning is designed to provide further practice	4.36	.546	Always
2. Applies previously learned or taught competencies	4.36	.546	Always
3. Connects link between concepts and skills and competencies	4.33	.538	Always
4. Upholds the right of the learner to education	4.24	.559	Always
5. Provides opportunities to learn	4.18	.527	Most of the Time
6. Provides an inclusive learning environment	4.20	.617	Most of the Time
7. Learning environment develops respect for child’s social and cultural identity.	4.23	.580	Always
8. Recognizes the active role of learners	4.23	.580	Oftentimes
9. Motivates learners to work productively	4.23	.580	Always
10. Motivates learners to work independently	4.23	.580	Always
Overall Mean	4.26	.565	Always

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Always/3.41-4.20 Most of the Time/2.61-3.40 Sometimes/1.81-2.60 Seldom/1.00-1.80 Never

Table 1.2 presents the mean distribution of national learning camp in terms of consolidation. Overall, the camp in terms of consolidation was rated as “Always” which means very highly practiced with the mean of 4.26 (SD= .565). which indicates that the learning focus is given to provide further practice of previously taught competencies which were not mastered by the learners. The program provides opportunities which allow learners to identify links connecting concepts and skill across grade-level competencies.

The indicators “Learning is designed to provide further practice” and “Applies previously learned or taught competencies” obtained the highest mean value of 4.36 (SD = .546) which implies that learning activities during the national learning camp was planned to provide practices and experiences that inspire learners to apply previous learning and competencies to new learning activities. It can be deduced that learning camps are not only effective in helping learners make up for the gaps and losses brought about by the pandemic, but they also help build a love of learning that can last a lifetime. According to Apurada (2023), the learning camp provides learners with the opportunity to explore new learning environment and develop important skills that will serve well in the future.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 4.18 (SD.527) is verbally described as “Most of the Time” in the indicator “Provides opportunities to learn” indicates that the learning camp provides the excellent opportunities for learners to learn in a new environment and learning atmosphere.

Apurada (2023) averred that in most occasions the school has shared the DepEd crusade in making learning more interesting, exciting, and informative to recover the learning losses by conducting the learning camp which provide opportunities to learners to learn in a new learning environment that more engaging learning experience that help pupils develop critical thinking, problem-solving abilities, and love to learning which eventually enabled them to become grade ready which will be validated by the post-assessment results.

Table 1.3 presents the mean distribution of national learning camp in terms of intervention. Overall, the respondents rated the camp as “Most of the Time” with the mean of 4.20 (SD=.546) which indicates that the type of camp designed to support most of the time to the needs of learners who are yet to grasp foundational skills in the basic learning areas such as English, Mathematics, and Science.

Mendoza (2023) asserted that learning camp provides opportunities to both pupils and teachers to revisit the pedagogy of learning assessment and evaluation which is predictive to the mastery of targeted competencies of each learning area or subject.

Table 1.3. Mean Distribution of National Learning Camp in terms of Intervention

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1. Provides interesting lessons for pupils' to master.	4.30	.465	Oftentimes
2. Facilitates mastery of basic academic skills such as reading, writing, speaking, and listening	4.29	.458	Always
3. Stimulates learner to work independently	4.23	.424	Always
4. Facilitates development of critical and creative thinking skills	4.24	.434	Always
5. Provides engaging performance tasks	4.26	.442	Always
6. Utilizes strategies that inspire pupils to master the least mastered competencies	4.16	.417	Most of the Time
7. Supports pupils achieve foundational skills in English and Math.	4.12	.484	Most of the Time
8. Helps pupils sustain learning motivation and engagement	4.12	.484	Most of the Time
9. Supports pupils use application of grade-level competencies.	4.12	.484	Most of the Time
10. Develops pupils' ability to fully grasp difficult concepts of the subject matter	4.12	.484	Most of the Time
Overall Mean	4.20	.456	Most of the Time

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Always/3.41-4.20 Most of the Time/2.61-3.40 Sometimes/1.81-2.60 Seldom/1.00-1.80 Never

The indicator “Provides interesting lessons for pupils to master” obtained the highest mean value of 4.30 (SD=.465) which imply that teachers in the national learning camp provide interesting and engaging lessons which help pupils develop mastery of the competencies.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 4.12 (SD=.484) is verbally described as “Most of the Time” in the indicators “Supports pupils achieve foundational skills in English and Mathematics”, “helps pupils sustain learning motivation and engagement”; “Supports pupils use application of grade-level competences”; and, “Develops pupils' ability to fully grasp difficult concepts of the subject matter”. These findings imply that teachers provide support for pupils to achieve the basic competencies in English and Math through sustained motivation and learning engagements.

Anamong (2021) affirmed that learning camp help pupils develop their ability to fully grasp difficult concepts in each learning area especially in improving mastery in English, Science, and Math.

Problem 2. What is the level of pupils' engagement of the different learning focus?

Table 2. Mean Distribution of Pupils' Engagement of the Different Learning Focus

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1. Pupil comes to the learning camp early	4.38	.490	Very Highly Engaged
2. Pupil participates in individual and group learning activities	4.40	.493	Very Highly Engaged
3. Pupil personally involved in group tasks	4.38	.490	Very Highly Engaged
4. Pupil shows enthusiasm, eagerness, and personal motivation in learning new tasks	4.36	.546	Very Highly Engaged
5. Pupil manifests skills improvement in the most mastered learning competencies	4.36	.601	Very Highly Engaged
6. Pupil interestingly involved in English language skills development especially reading	4.21	.599	Very Highly Engaged
7. Pupil interestingly involved in Mathematics/numeracy skills development	4.15	.618	Highly Engaged
8. Pupil interestingly involved in Science and discovery learning skills.	4.12	.599	Highly Engaged
9. Pupils' engagement and participation in the end-of-school year learning activities help enhance mastery of the least-mastered learning competencies in the learning areas.	4.12	.599	Highly Engaged
10. Pupil sustained enthusiasm in the self-learning activities for the whole duration of the program.	4.12	.599	Highly Engaged
Overall Mean	4.26	.563	Very Highly Engaged

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Very Highly Engaged/3.41-4.20 Highly Engaged/2.61-3.40 Moderately Engaged/1.81-2.60 Less Engaged/1.00-1.80 Not Engaged

Table 2 presents the mean distribution of pupils' engagement of different learning focus in the implementation of the National Learning Camp. Overall, the respondents rated the pupils as “Very Highly Engaged” with the mean of 4.26 (SD=.563) which indicates that the pupils were very highly engaged in the different learning focus during the conduct of the National Learning Camp and that they were actively participated in the different learning activities.

As Apurada (2023) had emphasized that the learning camp offered an enrichment, intervention, and remediation camp activities to pupils and the activities are highly engaging to the learning camp participants as it tries to help pupils make up for the gaps and losses of learning which was brought by the pandemic.

The indicator “Pupils participates in individual and group learning activities” obtained the highest mean value of 4.40 (SD=.493) which imply that pupils were very much engaged in the different activities in every learning focus and their collaboration to learning positively contributed to their rich learning experiences during the camp. Mendoza (2023) averred that pupils' engagement in the learning experiences in the learning camp may give new learning perspectives and may help intensify their learning interest.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 4.12 (SD=.599) is verbally described as “Highly Engaged” in the indicators “Pupils interestingly involved in Science and discovery learning skills”; “Pupils' engagement and participation in the end-of-school year learning activities help enhance mastery of the least mastered learning competencies in the learning areas”; and, “Pupil sustained enthusiasm in the self-learning activities for the whole duration of the program”. These findings imply that the learning camp participants were extremely

engaged in the different learning activities in different learning focus which they find more stimulating, challenging, and informative. Thus, it is imperative that the National Learning Camp is regularly be conducted in order to inspire learners' engagement and participation in the learning activities because learning is given in a new and interesting setting.

Mendoza (2023) avowed that learning camp inspires pupils' participation and collaboration in different learning activities because pupils find the new learning environment more stimulating, challenging, and informative.

Problem 3. What are the level of pupils' learning performance when they are categorized as; Outstanding, Very Satisfactory, Satisfactory, Fairly satisfactory, Did not meet expectation?

Table 3 presents the level of pupils' learning performance when they are categorized as Outstanding, Very Satisfactory, Satisfactory, Fairly Satisfactory, and Did not meet expectations.

Table 3. Frequency Distribution of Pupils' Learning Performance

<i>Performance</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Outstanding	14	22%
Very Satisfactory	19	29%
Satisfactory	22	34%
Fairly Satisfactory	10	15%
Did not meet Expectation	0	0
Total	65	100%

It can be asserted that out of 65 respondents 22 (34%) were rated Satisfactory (80-85%) while only 10 or 15% were rated Fairly Satisfactory. It can be asserted that more pupils manifest learning improvement in the learning camp where they were given a unique learning experiences in a more engaging, stimulating, and challenging learning environment.

Subsequently, the learning camp as an educational environment outside the more formal and traditional classroom setting where pupils engage in experiential learning activities is more exciting and motivating to pupils hence it encourages them to participate and collaborate learning.

As Apurada (2023) pointed out that pupils are more interested and excited to work and engage in learning activities outside of the traditional classroom because they will find the new learning environment more stimulating and challenging. Further, learning camp provides a more interesting, exciting, and informative learning atmosphere which provides opportunities to learners to learn in a new learning environment.

Problem 4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of pupils' learning performance and the extent of implementation of the National Learning Camp in terms of the following learning focus; Enhancement, Consolidation, and Intervention?

Table 4 indicates the interplay between the level of pupils' learning performance and the extent of the implementation of the National Learning Camp in terms of the following learning focus such as enhancement, consolidation, and intervention.

Table 4. Statistical Result of the Interplay Between the Pupils' Learning Performance and the Implementation of National Learning Camp

<i>Learning Focus</i>	<i>Pupils' Learning Performance</i>			
	<i>(r)</i>	<i>Sig</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>H01</i>
Enhancement	.560	.000	Signifies Moderate Correlation	Rejected
Consolidation	.729	.000	High Correlation	Rejected
Intervention	.029	.820	Denotes Negligible Correlation	Accepted

Table 4 presents the statistical results of the interplay between pupils' learning performance and the implementation of the national learning camp in terms of enhancement signifies moderate correlation to pupils' learning performance as evident by the computed r value of .560 which is greater than the significant value of .000. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Likewise, the learning focus in terms of Consolidation described to have high correlation to pupils' learning performance. The computed value which is .729 has a greater value than the significant value of .000. Therefore, null hypothesis was rejected.

On the other hand, the learning focus in terms of Intervention denotes negligible correlation to pupils' learning performance with a computed value of .029 which is less than the significant value of .820. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted.

To sum up, only the Enhancement and Consolidation affect closely to pupils' learning performance. It can be argued logically, that the pupils' learning performance was directly influenced by the two learning focus which lead them to perform reasonably.

Generally, a fairly satisfactory learning performance is the result of the more interesting, challenging, and stimulating learning activities provided or utilized by teachers. Thus, it is emphasized that appropriate learning activities in a more conducive, stimulating, and

engaging learning environment greatly influenced learning (Mendoza, 2023).

Problem 5. Is there a significant relationship between the level of pupils' learning performance and the extent of pupils' engagement to the different learning focus?

Table 5. *Statistical Result of the Interplay Between the Pupils' Learning Engagement and Pupils' Learning Performance*

<i>Learning</i>	<i>Pupils' Learning Performance</i>		
	<i>(r)</i>	<i>Sig</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Learning Engagement	.086	.496	Denotes Negligible Correlation
			Accepted

Table 5 presents the interplay between the pupils' learning performance and pupils' engagement of the different learning focus in the implementation of the national learning camp. The table depicts that pupils' learning engagement to the different learning focus denotes negligible correlation to pupils' learning performance as evident by the computed r value of .086 which is lower than the significant value of .496. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted. It can be argued logically, that the pupils' learning performance was not directly influenced by their engagements to different learning focus.

This finding was supported by Apurada (2023) who emphasized that pupils' learning performance is not only the significant factor that influence pupils' learning engagement to different learning focus because there are other attributes that best describe pupils' learning performance such as their mental and psychological readiness on academic tasks, personal motivation and their interest to learn, and parental support.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

The National Learning Camp predominantly demonstrated a positive influence on pupils' learning outcomes, although divergent views emerged regarding the extent of improvement especially in critical thinking skills. Further, the National Learning Camp adopts the learning recovery program which aims to strengthen the learning recovery and continuity program, improve literacy and numeracy, and accelerate the achievement of education targets. Improving literacy and numeracy skills is like opening a door to a world of knowledge and imagination. It helps pupils learn new things, improve language skills, and be better at understanding the world around them.

One of the best approaches of the Department of Education to address the challenges in education is to provide and promote the right of all citizens to qualify basic education and to make such education accessible to all by providing all Filipino children a free and compulsory education in elementary and secondary levels. However, the challenge in education is on the low performance of learners in English, Science, and Mathematics. The conduct of the summer camp known as the National Learning Camp is to help improve pupils' learning performance through out-of-the classroom learning which aims to strengthen the learning recovery and continuity learning modality to improve performance through the unstructured learning plan.

The implementation of the national learning camp can have positive effects on pupils' learning performance or learning outcomes by helping them acquire important skills through extensive learning engagement outside the classroom and creating positive social and psychosocial conditions for academic learning.

Based on the findings and conclusions presented, the following recommendations are suggested:

Department of Education (DepEd) Officials will provide learning strategies and encourage teachers through the learning area supervisors to craft the needed development framework to intensify pupils' learning performance through out-of-classroom learning activities.

School Principals/School Heads will be able to provide technical assistance to teachers in carrying out the learning camp especially in the administration and management of learning tasks.

Teachers as Instructional Leaders are recommended to develop their strategic intervention materials responsive to the development of least mastered learning competencies in English, Science, and Mathematics in a creative and more innovative learning to address the learning challenges in the teaching and learning process.

Parents will be able to provide support in the learning activities designed by teachers to improve their child's academic and learning performance. Parental support is indispensable in the academic success of their children, thus, the need to always encourage them to participate and collaborate with teachers in providing necessary learning support.

Community Officials/Other stakeholders will be able to intensify their support to school and learners especially in intensifying literacy and numeracy skills through the needed scaffolding framework or programs in order to develop resiliency among learners in addressing all the challenges in school and in learning.

Future Researchers will be encouraged to conduct a similar study on the influence of creative learning delivery through learning camps and the like to pupils' learning and academic performance so that they may be able generate a doable framework responsive to address the challenges in learning.

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